

Supplementary Information for:

A Novel Polar Zinc-based Hybrid Material: Structure, Properties, and Memristive Performance

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Small Structures

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Figure S1. ORTEP representation of the asymmetric unit of $(\text{CHA})_2[\text{ZnI}_4]$, drawn at the 50% probability level. The asymmetric unit consists of one $[\text{ZnI}_4]^{2-}$ anion and two cyclohexylammonium (CHA) cations as discrete ionic species. Zn, I, N, C and H atoms are depicted in green, purple, blue, grey and white, respectively. Hydrogen atoms are shown as spheres of arbitrary radius.

Figure S2. Details of the crystal structure of $(\text{CHA})_2[\text{ZnI}_4]$ showing the packing of the $[\text{ZnI}_4]^{2-}$ tetrahedra viewed along the ac and ab planes, respectively. The cyclohexylammonium (CHA^+) cations have been omitted for clarity.

Figure S3. Details of the crystal structure of $(\text{CHA})_2[\text{ZnI}_4]$ showing the packing of the cyclohexylammonium (CHA^+) cations viewed along the ac and cb planes. The two orientations of the disordered CHA^+ cations are depicted in black and blue for clarity. The $[\text{ZnI}_4]^{2-}$ tetrahedra have been omitted for clarity.

Figure S4. Detail of the crystal structure of $(\text{CHA})_2[\text{ZnI}_4]$ viewed along the ac plane, showing a single layer of $[\text{ZnI}_4]^{2-}$ tetrahedra and the two crystallographically distinct CHA^+ cations occupying different cavities. The ordered CHA^+ cation resides in a cavity defined by four $[\text{ZnI}_4]^{2-}$ tetrahedra — two belonging to a chain running along the c -axis and two from adjacent antiparallel chains — whereas the disordered CHA^+ cation occupies a smaller cavity formed by only three $[\text{ZnI}_4]^{2-}$ tetrahedra, located between two adjacent chains.

Figure S5. Powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD) pattern of $(\text{CHA})_2[\text{ZnI}_4]$ at room temperature as powder (blue line) and as thin film deposited onto a FTO substrate by antisolvent-assisted (toluene) spin-coating (green line). Both patterns are compared with the simulated pattern calculated from single-crystal X-ray diffraction data (black line).

Figure S6. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) curve of $(\text{CHA})_2[\text{ZnI}_4]$ recorded under a N_2 atmosphere at a heating rate of 10 K min^{-1} . The compound remains thermally stable up to $\sim 500 \text{ K}$, above which it undergoes a two-step decomposition process. The first step ($500\text{--}600 \text{ K}$, $\sim 60\%$ mass loss) is attributed to the release of two cyclohexylammonium iodide units, and the second step ($600\text{--}680 \text{ K}$, $\sim 40\%$ mass loss) corresponds to the decomposition of the remaining ZnI_2 residue.

Figure S7. Measured S-E loops for (CHA)₂ZnI₄ material. It is worth noting that no electromechanical response was observed.

Figure S8. a-c) Variability of the I - V response among different devices. d) Variability of a $(\text{CHA})_2[\text{ZnI}]_4$ memristor I - V response over 20 cycles.

Figure S9. Consecutive LTP/LTD cycles. Set voltage: 1 V, Read voltage: 0.1 V, Reset voltage: -1 V, pulse width: 100 ms.

Table S1. Crystallographic data and structure refinement for (CHA)₂[ZnI₄] compound at *T* = 100 and 293 K.

	(CHA) ₂ [ZnI ₄] <i>T</i> = 100 K	(CHA) ₂ [ZnI ₄] <i>T</i> = 298 K
CCDC number	2555355	2555354
Empirical formula	C ₁₂ H ₂₈ I ₄ N ₂ Zn	C ₁₂ H ₂₈ I ₄ N ₂ Zn
Formula weight	773.33 g/mol	773.33 g/mol
Temperature	100.00 K	293.00 K
Crystal system	orthorhombic	orthorhombic
Space group	Pna2 ₁	Pna2 ₁
<i>a</i>	12.5168(7) Å	12.7922(3) Å
<i>b</i>	21.4744(13) Å	21.2101(6) Å
<i>c</i>	8.2679(5) Å	8.4842(2) Å
α	90°	90°
β	90°	90°
γ	90°	90°
Volume	2222.3(2) Å ³	2301.97(10) Å ³
<i>Z</i>	4	4
ρ_{calc}	2.308 g/cm ³	2.231 g/cm ³
μ	3.518 mm ⁻¹	3.396 mm ⁻¹
F(000)	1419.0	1424.0
Crystal size	0.376 × 0.261 × 0.162 mm ³	0.376 × 0.261 × 0.162 mm ³
Radiation	AgK α (λ = 0.56086)	AgK α (λ = 0.56086)
2 θ range for data collection/°	3.944 to 55.726 °	4.08 to 41.04 °
Index ranges	-20 ≤ <i>h</i> ≤ 20, -35 ≤ <i>k</i> ≤ 35, -13 ≤ <i>l</i> ≤ 13	-15 ≤ <i>h</i> ≤ 15, -26 ≤ <i>k</i> ≤ 26, -10 ≤ <i>l</i> ≤ 10
Reflections collected	205201	32408
Independent reflections	10761 [R _{int} = 0.0632, R _{sigma} = 0.0210]	4678 [R _{int} = 0.0583, R _{sigma} = 0.0366]
Data / restraints / parameters	10761/260/246	4678/426/238
Goodness-of-fit on F ²	1.037	1.017
Final R indexes [<i>I</i> ≥ 2 σ (<i>I</i>)]	R ₁ = 0.0249, wR ₂ = 0.0530	R ₁ = 0.0515, wR ₂ = 0.1106
Final R indexes [all data]	R ₁ = 0.0274, wR ₂ = 0.0540	R ₁ = 0.0672, wR ₂ = 0.1215
Largest diff. peak/hole	1.11/-1.91 e Å ⁻³	1.15/-0.84 e Å ⁻³
Flack parameter	0.51(3)	0.5(2)